

Quantum Single Particle Bound Wavefunction As 1/ Equilibrium Normalization Factor

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We have argued in previous notes that both Newtonian mechanics and free particle quantum mechanics arise from special relativity. Thus, special relativity gives an expression for free particle energy and momentum and these are related to concepts of work. The Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ shows that x,t and $x+h\bar{p}/p$, $t+h\bar{E}/E$ give the same solution to this potential-like term showing that there is stochasticity in the position and time delivery of interaction hits. In other words, even though the center-of-mass moves as $x=vt$, a momentum hit (proportional to rest mass m_0) does not necessarily act at the center-of-mass. This gives the impression of shifts in probability, kinetic energy etc in the case of interference, i.e. interactions. For a single free particle, there is no interaction and $-1/2m d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx) = pp/2m \exp(ipx)$.

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability and that in general one may add independent probabilities in an OR situation as in a 2-slit interference case. A bound state, however, is different because even though one adds weighted $\exp(ipx)$ s, they are part of a resonance or equilibrium and this is no longer an independent OR situation. We suggest that one uses a conditional probability when computing a Newtonian nonrelativistic conservation of energy equation to try to remove as much of the quantum features from this equation. As a result, one has: $KE_{\text{classical}}(x) + V(x) = E = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } pp/2m P(p/x) + V(x)$.

One cannot bypass the fact that a quantum particle interacts differently from a classical one and that this involves a probabilistic granularity (wavelength), but classical notions of energy and energy conservation still exist. As a result, the bound state wavefunction $W_n(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a_n(p) \exp(ipx)$ is not a usual OR sum, but is rather 1 over a normalization factor for an equilibrium picture. As a result, one cannot use $W_{n1}(x)W_{n2}(x) = W_{(n1+n2)}(x)$ as one would for independent probabilities.

Furthermore, given that one has $W_n(x)$ and $W_{n1}(x)+W_{n2}(x)$ which are both of the form $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, and both represent average energies, one needs a way to distinguish a resonance/equilibrium from a sum of resonance/equilibrium normalization factors. We suggest that the orthogonality of resonance $W_n(x)$'s provides this feature. The standard textbook explanation is based on Hermitian operators, but in the nonrelativistic case, we argue that one may obtain the result based on integration by parts based on the form of the p operator = $-\text{grad}$. Thus, it is ultimately the form $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to orthogonal bound state $W_n(x)$'s, together with the boundary condition that $W_n(x) \rightarrow 0$ of $x \rightarrow +\text{infinite}$ and $-\text{infinite}$.

Classical Versus Quantum Physics

It is often argued that classical physics is the limit of quantum mechanics, but many classical physics concepts are present in quantum mechanical calculations at all energy levels. We argue that quantum mechanical and classical ideas coexist. In particular, a quantum free particle moves as $x=vt$. Even light is said to move a $x=ct$ even though it has a wavelength. Furthermore, special relativistic (classical) definitions of energy and momentum hold for all energy levels of usual quantum mechanics. For nonrelativistic kinetic energy, even a ground state is associated with $pp/2m$ with $\exp(ipx)$ and the Schrodinger equation is based on the classical conservation

conservation of energy using a potential $V(x)$ which represents energy at every point. What then makes quantum mechanics differ from classical mechanics? We argue that it is not concepts like energy or momentum, but rather the existence of an intrinsic spatial probabilistic probability associated with rest mass momentum hits and energy in time.

In particular, we suggest that both classical physics and free particle quantum mechanics follow from special relativity, which defines the energy and momentum of a particle with rest mass. It is the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px \quad ((1))$$

which allows for x,t and $x+h\bar{h}/p$, $t+h\bar{h}/E$ to render the same potential-like value suggesting that even though a free particle moves as $x=vt$, its hit (hence its energy or felt presence) may be shifted within a wavelength $h\bar{h}/p$. This is described by the probability

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((2))$$

For the case of an interaction with a 2-slit apparatus with slit spacing about $h\bar{h}/p$, this leads to a probabilistic OR adding of the probability for the particle going through one slit or the other. The probability to go through one slit or the other is independent, hence there are two probabilities in the problem:

((3a)) The intrinsic probability $\exp(ipx)$

((3b)) The independent probability to go through one slit or the other

Adding $\exp(ip \cdot r_1)$ and $\exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ (r_1 vector from slit one to a point on a screen far away) and ($r_2 =$ vector from slit two to a point on a screen far away) is a statistical OR situation.

We argue in this note, however, that simply adding various $\exp(ipx)$ s which carry weights which do not make them independent does not lead to regular probabilities, as in the case of a bound state wavefunction.

Before calculating a bound state wavefunction, we consider a free particle calculation:

$$E=pp/2m = - \frac{1}{\exp(ipx)} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) \frac{1}{2m} \quad ((4))$$

One sees that this is a conditional type of calculation because one multiplies $pp/2m$ by $\exp(ipx)$, but then divides by $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that this notion of conditional probability tries to extract the classical physics from the quantum because kinetic energy $pp/2m$ is essentially a classical result. If, however, one has interference of $\exp(ipx)$ s due to an interaction, one cannot completely remove quantum effects which is what seems to happen in a single particle bound state calculation.

Single Particle Bound State Calculation and the Role of the Wavefunction as an Equilibrium (Resonance) 1//Normalization Factor

We have argued that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability. One might then expect that adding probabilities is an OR situation, but this is not always the case, even in statistical mechanics. In particular, in an equilibrium (ideal gas) calculation:

$$\sum_i \exp(-E_i/T) \quad ((5))$$

represents the sum of unnormalized probabilities and ((5)) is 1/normalization factor for this equilibrium or resonance situation. We suggest that one has to know how to interpret a quantum bound wavefunction and not think of it as a probability.

In the quantum case, one adds $\exp(ipx)$'s which represent spatial interactions as these indicate at which point the particle interacts and hence at which point its energy is present. Given that this is a mathematical average calculation, one includes $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ together which gives the effect of removing probability and kinetic energy from some x regions and adding them to others. Otherwise, one has the usual conservation of energy. We note that the $\exp(ipx)$ s are not added as independent probabilities, but are highly dependent through:

$$\left\{ \sum_p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((6))$$

Here, there is the added condition that $W_n(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ tends to 0 for x tending to $\pm\infty$. The first term on the LHS of ((6)) is a conditional probability as one is really interested in only the kinetic energy at x .

As a result, one cannot consider $W_n(x)$ as a usual probability in the sense that:

$$W_{n1}(x) W_{n2}(x) \neq W_{(n1+n2)}(x) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{while } \exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((8))$$

The strong correlations between the weights of the $\exp(ipx)$ s means that $W_n(x)$ is 1/normalization of a resonance/equilibrium situation.

This begs the question: What happens if one writes:

$$A W_{n1}(x) + B W_{n2}(x)? \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is not a resonance-energy equilibrium state, but both $W_n(x)$ and ((9)) may both be written as:

$$\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

In textbooks, it is usually noted that if one has an eigenfunction of a Hermitian operator, then the eigenfunctions are orthonormal. Although this is true, we wish to find a stronger connection between the energy operator $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + V(x)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which gives rise to the operator $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$. We note that given $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ if one writes:

$\langle W1 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W2 \rangle$ one may use integration by parts and the vanishing of $W1, W2$ at $x=\pm\infty$ to write this as:

$$- \langle dW1/dx \ dW2/dx \rangle \quad ((11))$$

Thus, it is the form of $\frac{d}{dx}$ for the momentum operator and $\exp(ipx)$ itself which ultimately accounts for the fact that:

$$\langle W1 \ -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W2 \rangle + \langle W1 \ V \ W2 \rangle = E2 \langle W1 \ W2 \rangle \quad ((12a))$$

$$\langle W2 \ -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W1 \rangle + \langle W2 \ V \ W1 \rangle = E1 \langle W2 \ W1 \rangle \quad ((12b))$$

Here $W1, W2$ are real functions and $\langle \rangle$ means integral over dx .

Using integration by parts and subtracting yields: $\langle W1, W2 \rangle = 0 \quad ((13))$

The resonance $Wn(x)$'s are orthogonal which gives them a special feature.

We note that $P(x)_{\text{classical}} = Wn(x)Wn(x)$ yielding again a probability in space, but $Wn(x)$ itself is not a usual probability.

$\exp(-iEt)$ and Probability

Even though $Wn(x)$ does not act like a probability for products, its time dependent piece $\exp(-iEt)$ does as it only accounts for energy. $Wn(x)$ determines the details of the energy levels allowed, but then photons may be absorbed/emitted randomly and one may use usual statistical mechanics to describe such an interaction using the Boltzmann factor $\exp(-\Delta E/T)$ for a background temperature of photons of T . In this case:

$\exp(-iE1t)\exp(-iE2t) = \exp(-iE3t)\exp(-iE4t)$ as one deals simply with energy changes and not the details of the resonance.

Entropy Considerations

Typically, the literature creates Shannon entropy for the classical like probabilities:

$$W(x)W(x) = P(x) \quad \text{and} \quad a(p)a(p) = P(p). \quad ((14))$$

We have shown in previous notes that this is essentially equivalent to using

$P(x) P(-p/x)$ and then summing over p, x to obtain the sum of the two Shannon entropies listed above, i.e.

$$\sum_{x,p} W(x)W(x) a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x) \{ \ln(W) + \ln(a(p)) - ipx \}$$

$$= \sum_x W \ln(W) + \sum_p a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p)) - i \int dx W x d/dx W \quad ((15))$$

The real entropy portion is the sum of the two Shannon entropies one usually sees in the literature.

Given that the state W_n and E_n are obtained using only $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W$, we suggest that one could consider a Shannon's entropy based on this probability, but it is not clear how this would be linked with experiment, while the Shannon entropies of ((14)) are linked to measurables.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that both quantum and classical physics go hand in hand because both follow (or are directly linked) to special relativity. We consider $\exp(ipx)$ to be a probability and note that in the case of 2-slit interference, one may consider this as an OR case. For a single particle bound state one adds $\exp(ipx)$ s, but these are not independent probabilities, but are highly correlated to satisfy a classical conservation of energy equation using the conditional probability $P(p/x)$. In this case, $W_n(x)$, the wavefunction is 1/normalization of this equilibrium scenario, much like the partition function in classical statistical mechanics. As a result, one cannot simply consider $W_{n1}(x)W_{n2}(x) = W_{n1+n2}(x)$.